

1. Conceptual model illustrating the relationship between quantitative resistance to rice diseases and its components under natural pathosystem, IRRI, 1988. Presence of at least one compatible isolate is assumed.

2. General response curve of rice genotypes with differing levels of quantitative resistance (Q_nR) to rice disease potential levels, IRRI, 1988. VL = very low Q_nR , L = low, M = moderate, H = high, VH = very high.

quantitative resistance composed of high levels of two components will likely prove to have durable resistance, especially if pathogen isolates with virulence genes matched to genes for qualitative resistance have a low fitness in a given pathosystem.

The disease potential (pressure) in a particular crop is the sum of all varietal, agronomical, and edaphoclimatic conditions that affect the disease. No standard method to quantify disease potential has been developed yet. Nevertheless, disease potential can be estimated indirectly on the basis of disease severity in a cultivar chosen for

its intermediate partial resistance and low qualitative resistance. That cultivar will reflect changes over a wide range of disease potentials. Actual severity corresponding to low, moderate, or high disease levels will vary, depending upon the kind of disease.

The model in Figure 2 shows the response curves of varieties with different levels of quantitative resistance at different disease potential levels.

The terms "high" or "low" quantitative resistance are often used without clear definition. In our conceptual model, varieties with low or very low levels of quantitative resistance can be defined as those whose disease severity reaches maximum at low disease potential. Varieties with high or very high levels of quantitative resistance are those whose response curves only reach maximum at a very high disease potential (which may be rare under field conditions).

The relative differences between cultivars with different levels of

quantitative resistance will vary, depending on the disease potential (Fig. 2). Mass screenings of unknown genotypes can be made under moderate disease potential; fine differentiation among resistant cultivars should be made under moderately high disease potential. Under low disease potential, only low or very low levels of resistance can be differentiated.

Under high disease potential, varieties known to have high quantitative resistance suffer almost the same disease severity as known susceptible varieties. However, a remarkable difference in disease severity can be observed between cultivars with varying levels of resistance if disease potential is reduced (such as can be done with chemicals or by modifying cultural practices).

Quantitative resistance can therefore be a valuable component in integrated disease management, although it may not be sufficient by itself to control disease in certain agroclimatic regions. □

A method for scoring resistance to tungro (RTV)

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We used correlations between symptom severity and grain yield reduction to develop an effective scoring method for evaluating varieties for resistance to or tolerance for RTV infection.

Seedlings of nine varieties exposed to RTV-viruliferous green leafhoppers (GLHs) were transplanted in pots. Plants infected with both rice tungro bacilliform virus and rice tungro spherical virus (RTBV + RTSV), with RTBV alone, and with RTSV alone were identified by latex serology 1 or 2 wk after inoculation (WAI). Plant height was measured and symptoms were recorded 3 WAI.

Height and yield reductions were generally low in Balimau Putih, Palasithari, Sigadis, and Utri Rajapan, but high in BW272-6B, FK135, and TN1 (see table). Plants infected with

RTBV + RTSV had healthy appearances in Balimau Putih, light green coloration in Utri Rajapan, mild yellowing in Sigadis and Palasithari, and severe yellow-orange discoloration in the other varieties. RTBV-infected plants generally showed milder discoloration than doubly infected plants. RTSV-infected plants showed no discoloration and very mild stunting. Irrespective of variety, plants infected with RTBV + RTSV had the greatest reduction in height and yield followed by RTBV-infected plants. The correlations between yield and height reductions among plants infected with RTBV + RTSV or with RTBV or RTSV alone were significant in BW272-6B, FK135, and TN1, but not in Balimau Putih, Sigadis, and Utri Rajapan. Apparently, plants with severe symptoms had greater yield reduction.

These results indicate that the level of tolerance for RTV can be scored at about 3-4 WAI on the basis of plant height reduction and degree of leaf discoloration.

Symptoms and plant height reduction at 3 WAI, and grain yield reduction in plants of 6 cultivars infected at 1 wk after soaking, with RTBV + RTSV, RTBV alone, or RTSV alone. IRRI, 1988.

Cultivar	Virus	Symptoms ^a	Height reduction (%)	Yield reduction (%)
Balimau Putih	RTBV + RTSV	-	9.2	19.9
	RTBV	-	3.3	17.1
	RTSV	-	1.5	7.2
BW272-6B	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, D	62.6	94.2
	RTBV	S, Y	59.4	81.9
	RTSV	-	16.3	14.5
FK135	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I, D	72.0	99.0
	RTBV	S, Y, I, D	68.2	98.0
	RTSV	-	2.9	19.5
Palasithari	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I	36.9	33.5
	RTBV	S, Y	34.6	20.6
	RTSV	-	4.5	10.1
Sigadis	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I	16.9	30.7
	RTBV	-	13.5	23.9
	RTSV	-	11.2	9.1
Utri Rajapan	RTBV + RTSV	s, t	29.4	28.8
	RTBV	-	21.8	16.8
	RTSV	-	2.3	1.6
TNI	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I	71.8	97.4
	RTBV	S, Y, I	49.1	94.7
	RTSV	-	3.7	19.5

^aS = severe stunting, s = mild stunting, Y = yellow orange discoloration, y = mild yellowing, I = inter-veinal chlorosis, D = drooping of leaves, t = reduced tillering, - (dash) = no clear symptoms.

Frequency distribution of infection rates and scores of 1,117 rice germplasm tested by the modified mass screening method. IRRI, 1988.

Using these results, we modified the greenhouse mass screening method as follows:

1. Seed 20 germinated seeds of each entry in a pot.
2. Allow vector leafhoppers (GLH) to feed 3-4 d on RTV-infected plants.
3. Confine 7- to 10-d-old seedlings of 16 entries in a cage with 8-10 viruliferous GLH/ seedling for 3 h.
4. Consecutively inoculate 2 additional sets of entries.
5. Allow the viruliferous GLH to feed overnight on RTV-infected plants,

then use them again for inoculation.

6. Score seedlings individually 3-4 WAI.

Score symptom severity as follows:

- 1 = no symptoms
 - 3 = 1-10% plant height reduction with no leaf discoloration
 - 5 = 11-30% plant height reduction with no distinct leaf discoloration
 - 7 = 31-50% plant height reduction and/ or yellow to orange leaf discoloration
 - 9 = more than 50% plant height reduction and yellow to orange leaf discoloration
7. Compute average score.
 8. Select all entries for which average score is lower than 4 and index plants in ELISA for presence of RTBV and RTSV.

Cultivars with scores lower than 3 were considered resistant (or tolerant); cultivars with scores of 5, moderately resistant. We tested more than 1,000 rice germplasm using this modified mass screening method. Nine percent had

scores 0-3 (see figure). Tjempo Kijik (Acc. no. 16602) and Utri Merah (Acc. no. 16682) exhibited very mild symptoms but had high infection with RTBV and/or RTSV. □

Reaction of rice to yellow dwarf disease (YDD) and green leafhopper (GLH)

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To identify sources of resistance to YDD and its GLH vector *Nephotettix virescens*, seedlings of 35 rice varieties were inoculated by 5 YDD-viruliferous leafhoppers per plant for 24 h. The varieties also were tested against GLH, using the standard bulk seedling damage rating test.

Popular local rice varieties showed high susceptibility to the YDD pathogen (41.7-100% infection). NLR139-69, RP1931-54, and Tadukan had no infection. RP1931-54 and Tadukan also were resistant to GLH. NLR139-69 was resistant to YDD infection but susceptible to GLH. Kalinga-1 showed high resistance to GLH but 25% YDD infection. IR20, IR50, and TKM6 were resistant to GLH but showed 83, 67, and 58% YDD infection, respectively. □

Genetic analysis of bacterial blight (BB) resistance in Madhya Pradesh, India

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We evaluated about 7,000 rice accessions being maintained at Zonal Rice Research Station, Raipur, for field resistance to BB in 1982, when BB natural infection was very severe. The 204 entries found to be relatively free of disease were tested for resistance to 4 Philippine races of BB at Los Baños in